

Multimodal Analysis Of Covid 19 Visual Messages In Pakistan And India: A Comparative Study

Kanwal Gulzar, Imdad Ullah Khan, Saira Asghar Khan, Saood Khan, Iqra Mumtaz

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 28, 2021

Accepted:
July 20, 2021

Keywords :
COVID19, Visuals,
Multimodality,
Semiotics, Public
Messages. Discourse
Analysis

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5116588

Abstract

Multimodal analysis is helpful to unveil the hidden meaning of the verbal and visual texts. This study aims to carry out a multimodal analysis of visuals that were published to send out public service messages for society to tackle the emergent issue of Covid19. Public message ads of two countries are collected for the analysis. A comparative analysis has been conducted to study semiotic aspects of COVID19 visuals of two Asian countries i.e. Pakistan and India. A descriptive study is conducted employing van Leeuwen model for socio semiotics (1996). The findings of the study suggest that India has employed such visuals which convey fear among people whereas Pakistan has used motivational messages through visuals to combat the disease.

Introduction

The emergence of discourse analysis during the 1970s emphasized more on language along with its forms. It can be said that all semiotic resources such as images, sounds, and space have largely been ignored. According to O'Halloran, this is an "impoverished view" of discourse. The multimodal analysis considers the analysis of all types of texts including visuals, images, colors, texture, and tone. It also conveys the meaning hidden behind the visuals and brings out the best advertising effects. Many experts have researched multimodal discourses. It can also be noted that multimodal has taken its foundation from Halliday's (1994) SFL (Systemic functional linguistics) and this results in providing new avenues and dimensions for discourse analysis. Hence, in this way, multimodal discourse analysis has been the focus of many researchers especially in the field of linguistics and socio semiotics. Kress and van Leeuwen (1996; 2001), Lemke (1998), Royce (1998), Halloran (1999). Since the last two decades, importance has been given to analyze these modes of communication in terms of the meaning-making process. Among these modes, a mode that is given more importance is visual discourse via the use of images. There has been good research conducted on visual discourse analysis, but the most widely recognized model to study multimodality of verbal and visual texts is Kress and Van Leeuwen's semiotic theory (2006).

The world has encountered a globalized pandemic in the shape of COVID19. The media is playing a major role to generate public awareness messages either to emotionally boost them up psychologically or they are further trying to isolate people by frightening them through different visual messages. With the growing scenario of COVID19 across the world, countries are using different modes of communication to convey messages either through verbal texts or visuals, or both. Every country is using its way of generating the message in such a way that every visual is a complete depiction of its own culture and norms through its linguistics choices.

Pakistan and India are Asian countries, but they are following different cultures i.e. language style, values, religion, dress, color. Both of these countries have employed their styles or modes to convey coronavirus-related public awareness messages to the masses, which in turn reflects their mindsets. This comparative study aims to analyze visuals or images generated by these two countries. It aims to see whether these visuals convey similar or different messages. It will analyze whether the language is used similarly or differently by the two countries. It will also attempt to find the semiotic aspects found in visuals presented by the two countries.

1. Literature review

Kress and Van Leeuwen (1996) have proposed and developed a method of social semiotics analysis with perspectives of visual communication; a model of multimodality has been established by them. Semiotics refers to the relationship between signs and the things towards which they refer to generate meanings.

It is the interpretation of meaning by looking at the signs like words, symbols, and images that communicate many meanings. As this is the fact that our society is so much influenced by media messages, in the scenario semiotics contribute to this means of communication either visually or textually. Moreover, semiotics is interconnected with every aspect of human modes of communication i.e. sight, taste, hearing, touch, and smell. Thus we can say that it can be best analyzed by human beings who have innate potentials to produce and understand signs of all kinds.(Crystal, 2008).

Visuals are images that can represent the culture, history, and politics of people at different locations in a powerful memorable manner.As mentioned above, Kress and van Leeuwen proposed models for multimodal discourse that are used in the semiotic analysis. Taking the idea of Halliday's(1994) social semiotics, Kress and Van Leeuwen developed a method for visual communication analysis through social somatic and also developed the descriptive method for multimodal discourse. Van Leeuwen(2004) described three metafunctions for multimodal analysis

A) Representational meaning

According to van Leeuwen (1996), any semiotic system reveals representations that are external to the world through systems of signs. We can say that the semiotic system begins with the relationship between objects and the world beyond the representational system. Also, there are two categories (1) Narrative (2) Conceptual. The visuals help in producing representational meaning by looking at the details of participants and their role in the visuals.

B) Compositional meaning

Compositional meaning reflects all meanings that link both the internal and external context of visuals in which they are created.It gives an analysis of visual and verbal elements present in the image that makes a compositional whole. The visuals are analyzed according to horizontal structure and vertical structure.it also involves gaze, color, tone, elements of the visuals, and how they create function towards a meaning-making process of the visual.

C) Interactive Meaning

Interactive meaning is a semiotic system that shows the relationship between the producers of the image and the receiver of that image (Kress and Van Leewen,1996). In this particular metafunction, the social relationship is to be analyzed with an angle of producer, the viewer, and the object represented. All three aspects are important to generate meanings adhere to the context in which they are established.

It is important to mention that all types of messages when looking at the shop's signs, billboards, traffic lights, brand logos, billboards, and even posters are being generated to convey meanings everywhere. Semiotics has been a very useful tool that contributes to generating meaningful meanings in influential ways in any culture. As we know society is influenced by media messages either they are texts or visuals. Semiotics helps human beings to interpret all images or texts by using their innate capacities to produce and interpret all kinds of signs. This interpretation is taken by Al Zubaidi and Abdullah (2018) who conducted their study of studying semiotics across cultures and shop signs of Iraqi and American in their contexts. They have analyzed 40 Iraqi and American Cafe and restaurant signs, the findings reveal both cultures have represented their cultures equally through visual and verbal texts.

Some famous researchers have done studies in line with multimodal discourse analysis. Kress (1996; 2001; 2006),O'Toole (1994), Van Leeuwen (2005; 2006),and O'Halloran (1999)documented multi-model analyses regarding social semiotics.t can be said that multimodal analysis is performed through visual images in which images are analyzed to see how figures, places, and things interact with visual design to integrate to form compositional, representational, and interactive meanings. All previous studies document multimodal analysis from different perspectives. There are many researchers conducted on textual and visual analysis of different genres, namely advertisements, public service messages, magazine images, music.

1.1. COVID19 Public Awareness Messages

COVID19 is a deadly virus that has now become a pandemic across the world. There have been different visuals generated to convey an awareness message. All these messages tell you to fight the disease similarly or rather differently. The purpose behind such advertisements is to influence the views and behaviors of society by attracting the viewers' attention by using diverse artistic representation styles. All components of the images collaborate with viewers to transfer the message specific to a particular genre. This study analyses the awareness ads of COVID19 keeping in mind three tenets advocated by Kress & Van Leeuwen (1996). This comparative study will look into the visuals presented by two countries; Pakistan and India. Although the visuals are generated for the same purposes, this study aims to encode the messages hidden behind the text to analyze the similarities and differences of two different countries. Specific research questions explored in the current study include:

- 1.What aremultimodal aspects of COVID19 visuals presented in two selected Asian countries?
- 2.Is the language used in visuals of two selected countries convey similar messages or different messages?

2. Methodology

This study is descriptive and comparative. Four samples of visuals are collected through purposive sampling. This is a qualitative study. The selected visuals are collected from two Asian countries, Pakistan and India. Cook (2001) has identified that the function of advertisements is to inform, and influence and probably change opinions, emotions, and attitudes. Thus to check how this is being achieved in these selected public service messages, the socio semiotic model of Kress & Van Leeuwen (1996) has been adopted to analyze multi-modal visuals and their relation with the language used in those visuals.

3. Data Analysis

The visuals will be analyzed concerning the three aspects described in van Leeuwen's theoretical framework (1996) – visual contact, social distance, modality. Then the verbal text will be analyzed individually. Later, this study will also analyze the relationship between visuals and verbal text.

4.1. First visuals in India

4.1.1. Visual contact

It can be considered as a demanding image or probably an image that shows an offer. It can be seen that all the represented participants in this image are conveying a message to the viewers and they are looking straight at the audience. Also, in any visuals, a participant's gaze demands the audience to enter into their world of contemplation and feel the intensity of the pandemic spread across the country. That is to say that represented participants want to establish a social relationship with the viewers upon the matter of the infectious disease coronavirus. The represented participants i.e. the coronavirus, a flag of India designed on a mask are looking at the audience and want to convey some sort of message for the safety of all Indian nationals. According to Chris and Van Leeuwen (1996), such an image offers that the participants which are represented, to the viewers as objects of contemplation items of information, and display information to much of the audience's knowledge. So here are participants of this visual, are required to think upon, provide information of prevention to the audience. The readers should understand this information, which is about the COVID-19 pandemic. Hence, the message is given to all Indian nations. It is addressed to protect themselves from getting infected. They should wear masks on their faces.

4.1.2. Social distance

The participants of this visual are divided into two parts, the coronavirus and the mask with a flag of India on it. The coronavirus has surrounded the mask from all sides. The mask with the printed Indian map looks quite prominent, whereas the virus is small in shape and approaching the mask from all sides. We can say that the Indian mask is a short shot having close interaction with the viewer whereas the virus looks quite small as compared to the size of the mask. Only two are at the medium shot, whereas the rest three are at a long shot, they are socially distant from the audience. Another important point is that the mask with an Indian flag attached to it gives a very meaningful message to all viewers.

4.1.3. Modality

The modality refers to how visuals are contextualized through their brightness, color and tone, gestures, and the size of participants. The flag of India presents four colors, the saffron color on the top symbolizes the courage and strength of the nation. The white color shows truth, peace and the blue wheel in the middle represents growth. This Ashoka Chakra wheel that has 24 spokes reveals 24 hrs. And the green color shows life and prosperity. The mask imprinted with an Indian flag shows that the progress, peace, growth, and strength of the nation is deeply

contextualized with a mask suggests that all viewers should use a mask to protect themselves 24 hours from this virus. The color of the virus is red which symbolizes bloodshed and danger. As we can see that the coronavirus is approaching the Indian mask reveals that the whole country is surrounded by danger. Also, there is equally a danger of getting ill or infected which might lead to the death of people.

4.1.4. Verbal image

The phrase written at the bottom of the visual is a message to its viewers ‘preventyourself’ which means it's addressing everyone who is looking at this image. Another phrase “from coronavirus” is written in a large font and in bold. This shows the producer’s emphasis by providing information and, writing the virus name so prominently. It is for readers to be careful about this harmful and dangerous virus. Another text that is written in the middle of the visual is ‘Dreams time’, it is written with a light color so it does not look so prominent in the whole visual.

4.1.5. Relation between visual and verbal

The compositional aspect is the relationship between the verbal and the visual image. From this visual, it is very clear that the text and the visual are having a strong relationship with each other. It might be taken as a kind of warning for viewers to protect themselves from this disease by wearing the mask as a precaution.

4.2. Second Visual in India

4.2.1. Visual Contact

This visual is taken as an offer image. As a very meaningful narrative is being conveyed to all its viewers. The participants of this visual are a man standing behind the big coronavirus-shaped Car, one big wall and one small wall, with a tree which is out of the reach of viewers’ eye. The whole image through its participants conveys an item of information for its viewers. The man is wearing a mask and a cap, he is looking at the viewers. He has lifted his two arms and showing the fingers as a sign of victory.

4.2.2. Social Distance

The participants (coronavirus car) are standing at a medium shot on the road, i.e. socially at a medium distance from viewers. Whereas the man is standing at a long shot behind the participant, i.e. coronavirus car. The door of the car is opened and a man lifts his two arms showing signs of victory to viewers. He is looking directly at viewers and looks confident.

4.2.3. Modality

The modality brings in the contextualization, tone, colors, brightness, gaze, the body language of the participants in the visuals. It can be seen that the color of the coronavirus car is green at its body, with black spots, and with red pointed edges. It shows the contrast between life and death. Green with black spots shows life at risk whereas red symbolizes death or danger. So, a car represents a whole showing means of transport carrying a message of life and death. The color of the road is grey that symbolizes a cool and balanced color. The green corona car is highlighted in grey color showing its powerful representation on viewers. On the other side, a man is wearing a white shirt with a cap symbolically representing truthfulness and purity. We can say

that he is truthful in his actions for making a car that looks like a structure of coronavirus. The message underlying is to make people scared enough from this moving car so that they can take necessary precautions and stay indoors.

4.2.4. Verbal text

The declarative sentence “India's moving ‘coronavirus’ on mission” is written in white. All words are written in bold letters and are in upper case. This shows that the producer of this visual wants all viewers to emphasize these words. Another point is that Coronavirus is written in inverted commas. This shows that this word is given specific emphasis as compared to other words in the sentence. Also, India is written with apostrophes showing possession. So, this indicates that India owns this virus and has developed a means of transport to give it a real physical shape. Moreover, one more point which is important to notice is that the use of the word ‘On Mission’ is referred to as ‘coronavirus’. This gives the message that there is some goal behind making this moving coronavirus which may be to keep people indoors during the COVID19 pandemic by making them afraid of the physical look of the car. Also, there is another phrase written on the moving car that is ‘Sudha Cars’, it is the name of the developer of this car.

4.2.5. Relation between Visual and verbal

The relationship between visual and verbal is significantly meaningful. The text implies a powerful stance over viewers to get an idea about how India as a nation is striving hard to combat the ongoing pandemic. By making a car that helps to keep people inside the home during lockdown situations.

4.3. First visual in Pakistan

Pakistan is showing good efforts through language on visuals to combat the COVID19 pandemic. The following analysis focuses on examples of public visuals used in Pakistan to raise awareness about COVID19 and ensure public safety.

4.3.1 Visual contact

This visual is counted as an offer image or demand image as represented participants are presenting information to the viewers. This visual offers all participants to provide necessary coronavirus information. This image is divided into two parts. The first part is the Pakistani flag enclosed in a shield and the second is the biological structure form of coronavirus in the background. On the left side is the language part. Concerning the visual, the producer of this image wants all viewers to make connections between the Pakistani symbolic flag inscribed in the two-layered protective shields from the novel coronavirus and the language written on its left side.

4.3.2. Social distance

The shield with the Pakistani flag is at medium-short indicates a socially distant relationship with viewers. Whereas the coronavirus is far long shot indicates an impersonal relationship with viewers. The shield looks bigger than the coronavirus showing that this shield with the Pakistani flag inscribed in it has a powerful impact as compared to infectious virus.

4.3.3. Modality

The modality deals with contextualization, brightness, color, size. Pakistani flag is of green color in its base with white moon and crescent looking at top of the logo. The white color represents purity. The size of the crescent and moon is comparatively prominent in that visual. Brown colored and two-layered shields have enclosed the moon crescent showing as it has protected Pakistan from outside. On the other side, there is a coronavirus i.e. two big and two are small, looking at the background which has a closed contact with the shield. The green

color symbolizes life. Whereas the color of the virus is black symbolizes darkness and evil. This might indicate that rightful life is powerful to dominate darkness.

4.3.4 Verbal Text

The language used in the visual is English and Urdu. The text is written in green, black, and white color. The Urdu message is written in bold with green color “corona se darnainlarna ha” (do not be afraid of the corona) has some motivational message for a Pakistani nation. There is another message saying “corona k bary main janny k liye” (to get corona information) this message is linked with the website address given at the right bottom. They are offering this facility to all viewers to gather more information from the mentioned websites. On the left, the word Pakistan is written in the Urdu language with white color, looks more prominent than words written in black “mazboot and sehatmand”. Viewers have emphasized this message that this country does have the potential to beat the difficult times as they are confronting a deadly virus nowadays. Similarly, there is another message given at the left bottom in the black text. A bold and upper-case font is used. “A STEP TOWARDS SAFE PAKISTAN” another encouraging message given for viewers to be hopeful in this situation. There is another message in Urdu for viewers “ehtiyatilaj se behtarhai”, another indirect message for an audience to take careful precautions in this situation. There are two logos, i.e. one is at the right bottom NITB. The other is the logo of govt of Punjab with three Urdu words written inside it “ittehademaan and tanzeem” (trust, faith, and discipline).

4.3.5. Relation of visual and verbal text

The relation between visual text and verbal text of this discourse shows a deep underlying meaning for all viewers. The messages conveyed in the above visual have four different discourses.

- A motivational message to all Pakistani viewers that “corona se darnainlarna ha”.
- A message to distribute information about the website to collect more information about this deadly disease and its precautions.
- A message about following SOPs “ehtiyatilaj se behtar ha” (prevention is better than cure) for the public to be careful.
- A message for Pakistani people from the government of Pakistan about the good steps they are taking to combat the virus.

4.4. Second Visual in Pakistan

4.4.1 Visual contact

This visual is taken as an offer image where participants are delivering their stance about the lockdown situation during the COVID19 pandemic. As you can see in this visual, the stethoscope, which is a medical instrument to check the heartbeats of patients, is wrapped around a parallel white strip. Moreover, a little lock is placed between written text. The other participant is a logo at the bottom.

4.4.2. Social Distance

It has two participants i.e. a parallel strip is at the short shot and both ends go beyond the viewer's reach giving some background information, and the other is a stethoscope in which few parts are out of reach of viewers to give some background meaning. It is at a medium shot. This indicates that it is not so distant socially.

4.4.3 Modality

All represented participants are contextualized with each other to give some underlying meaning. The background color is sea green with white lines on it. This color symbolizes calmness and relaxation. Whereas white shows purity. This visual conveys the pure message of remaining cool and calm in this difficult time. The color of the text is red and sea green.

There is a logo at the bottom Karachi Port Trust 1887 is an organization in Pakistan. It is the logo of the trust which created this visual. The logo has a central vertical line with little at its edge and is surrounded by a circle. The colors are red blue and white. That symbolizes some sort of alarming situation during the calm period. Further, the color of the stethoscope is black and white gives the comparison of darkness and light. Few parts of the stethoscope cannot be seen by viewers and give an object of contemplation to viewers to think.

4.4.4 Verbal Text

The verbal text is connected with the color and other participants. Three different discourses are conveyed in this visual. First is the motivation message that says "IT'S NOT LOCKDOWN, it's to knock CORONA DOWN". Encouraging words in this message during COVID19 lockdown. It does not frighten people from Coronavirus but motivates them to keep their morale up to fight this virus. The red color symbolizes danger. The text is written in bold and uppercase for viewers. This shows that the producer wants to emphasize this message. The second text is written in red color with CORONAVIRUS written in bold, again the creator like all audiences give importance to this name of virus. From this text, the producer shows solidarity with all Pakistani viewers to fight against this disease together. The third text is about precaution #STAY HOME #STAY SAFE. This precautionary message is a globalized public awareness message that can be viewed in every spoken and written discourse.

4.4.5 Relation between visual and verbal text

The visual and the written text interpret Pakistan's media effort to fight against the disease and at the same time, they are treating all those who are ill from this virus. It can also be interpreted in this way that the motivational messages are closer to the heart of the producer of this image and he or she wants to convey his encouraging texts to all Pakistani people so that they should not be feeling frightened and weak to get ill from this virus.

5. Conclusion

This is a descriptive qualitative study. Two samples of visuals were collected purposively from each country i.e. Pakistan and India. Through semiotic analysis of the selected visuals, it can be observed that how these two countries use language to spread public awareness messages for the same reason that is COVID19. After analyzing the visuals, it can be seen clearly that both countries try to convey some messages but the purpose behind delivering the message is different. India attempts to frighten their public from the deadly coronavirus and urge them to stay indoors by making a car-shaped coronavirus that moves around in streets so that people don't come out from their homes. Whereas Pakistani visuals convey messages to boost up the spirits of Pakistanis to fight against the disease. They don't make people feel scared of this deadly virus. Rather they encourage people to hold their energies to fight against this virus. The Pakistani government is trying to fight and motivate the people. They do not want their people to lose hope in this difficult time. They are trying to convey such persuasive messages that are encouraging people to stay hopeful. On the other hand, the Indian Government is trying to horrify their nation by making frightening things so that they stay indoors, do not leave their homes. These results help to make a concluding remark that Pakistan is a courageous nation than India. Making a corona-shaped car is an example for the whole Indian nation to get scary, not making anything positive to boost their psychology.

The analysis of the above visuals gives a clear image of the difference between the two countries i.e. Pakistan and India. Through images, we can notice that India does not motivate or encourage its people to fight and unite to win against the coronavirus which has spread across the globe. India tries to frighten its people against this disease through images of masks and car-shaped coronavirus. The producers of images in India use the words like "prevent" and "India's moving coronavirus" clearly show the style of presenting facts to its audience. Moreover, they have not put more discourses in their visuals. On the other hand, Pakistan has used motivational words and phrases like "corona se dar nani lar na ha", "it's not a lockdown, it's to knock corona down" are encouraging texts written to keep the morale of its people up. Instead of frightening the people from the virus, Pakistani producers of the above visuals try to show solidarity to combat this virus. This shows a different approach to fighting against a pandemic than the one adopted by Indian producers of COVID19-related public text messages.

6. Future scope

This paper highlights the significance of a multimodal approach to the analysis of socially significant public messages at the time of crisis such as a global pandemic. However, this methodology can also be usefully employed to study visual messages in less challenging situations. Examples are advertisement billboards in public spaces that are meant for commercial advertisement purposes. Such messages can also be analyzed fruitfully by employing the methodology demonstrated in this article. Similarly, there are other avenues such as social media where visual messaging in still and video forms have a significant social significance in our current times. These messages can be analyzed through a multimodal semiotic analysis to uncover the reasons for their public appeal or lack thereof.

References

- Abdullah Al-Rawe, Marwah & Al-Zubaidi, Nassier. (2018). Semiotics across Cultures: An Analysis of Shop Signs in American and Iraqi Contexts. *Al-Adab Journal*. 22(1), 31-48.
- Cook, G. (2001). *Discourse of Advertising*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Crystal, D. (2008). *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell
- Halliday, M. (1994). *An introduction to functional grammar*. London, UK: Edward Arnold.
- Kress, G. and van Leeuwen, T. (1996). *Reading Images: The grammar of visual design*. London, UK: Routledge.

- Kress, G. and van Leeuwen, T. (2001). *Multimodal Discourse: The modes and media of contemporary communication*. London, UK: Arnold.
- Kress, G, Van Leeuwen, T (2006) *Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Lemke, J. Multiplying meaning: Visual and verbal semiotics in scientific text. In Martin, J. & Veal, R. (eds.), *Reading Science: Critical and Functional Perspectives on Discourses of Science* (pp. 87-113). London, UK: Routledge.
- O'Halloran, K. (1999). Independence, interaction and metaphor in multimodal texts. *Social semiotics.*, 9(3), 317-354.
- O'Halloran, K. (1999). Towards a systemic-functional analysis of multi-semiotic mathematics texts[J]. *Social Semiotic*. 124(2), 1-29
- O'Toole, M. (1994). *The language of displayed art*. London, UK: Leicester University Press.
- Royce, T. D. (1998). *Synergy on page: Exploring inter-semiotic complementarity in page-based multimodal text*. Tokyo: Japan Association of Systemic Functional Linguistics.
- Scollon, R. and Scollon, S. (2003). *Discourses in Place: Language in the Material World*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- vanLeeuwen, T (2006) Towards a semiotics of typography. *Information Design Journal*, 14(2): 139–155.
- vanLeeuwen, T (2005) *Introducing Social Semiotics*. London, UK: Routledge.

Author Information

Kanwal Gulzar

Fatima Jinnah Women University, Pakistan

ImdadUllah Khan

(corresponding author), University of Swat, Pakistan

SairaAsghar Khan

Fatima Jinnah Women University, Pakistan

Saood Khan

University of Swat, Pakistan

IqraMumtaz

University of Lahore, Pakistan